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Regulatory Impact of Prepaid Metering on Sustainable Urban Living

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Abstract: This study investigates the regulatory impact of widespread adoption of prepaid electricity metering on sustainable urban living in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1, 7 and 11. Using panel data (2017-2021) covering four regions of the Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG), Fixed and Random Effects regression models are used to assess the influence of meter deployment on power theft and QOS complaints. Data were sourced from the Public Utilities Regulatory Commission (PURC), Ghana Audit Service, ECG, and Ghana Statistical Service. The analysis reveals a statistically significant positive relationship between prepaid meter deployment, power theft, and QOS complaints. Interestingly, higher enrolment in Senior High Schools (SHS) correlates with increased theft cases, suggesting that greater technical literacy may facilitate tampering, especially within urban-poor communities. We find that prepaid metering may inadvertently worsen consumer hardship and undermine urban sustainability goals without consumer education and targeted support measures. Policymakers should adopt a balanced approach integrating deployment with interventions to ensure equitable access to safeguard consumer welfare. The study proposes instalment-based prepaid meter payment options that allow users to retain service. These recommendations emphasize the need for urban utility reforms integrated with urban planning for inclusive and sustainable living urban human settlements.

Keywords: Prepaid Metering, Power Theft, Quality of Service, Sustainable Urban Living

Main highlights:

- i. Prepaid meter deployment linked to increased power theft.
- i. Quality-of-service complaints rise with prepaid meter deployment.
- ii. Economic vulnerability drives illicit electricity use.
- iii. Technical faults and meter adaptation result in complaints.
- iv. A prepaid meter deployment policy is needed to achieve SDGs 1, 7, and 11.

Abbreviations (if required)

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Abbreviation	Meaning
BC	Billing Complaints
DC	Disconnection Complaints
EC	Energy Commission
ECG	Electricity Company of Ghana
FE	Fixed Effect
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GSS	Ghana Statistical Services
MC	Metering Complaints
MCA	Millennium Challenge Account
MD	Meter Deployment
MIDA	Millennium Development Authority
MMS	Meter Management System
NE	Net Enrolment
PPM	Pre-Payment Meters/Prepaid Meters
PT	Power Theft
PURC	Public Utilities Regulatory Commission
QOS	Quality of Service
QOSC	Quality of Service Complaints
RE	Random Effect
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SHS	Senior High School

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1.0 Introduction

The global energy landscape is undergoing a significant transformation driven by demands for sustainability (Gershon, 2025) and enhanced service delivery (Dechamps, 2023). Fundamental to this evolution is the adoption of electricity metering infrastructure, often manifesting as prepaid or smart metering systems. These technologies portend many benefits for utility providers in terms of improved revenue collection and enhanced demand-side management (Banerjee et. al, 2016; Jacome and Ray, 2018). For consumers, the possible advantages include greater control over energy consumption expenditure. Prepaid metering could enhance revenue assurance in the provision of sustainable energy, but its effects in urban-poor contexts remain insufficiently explored.

Ghana, a West African nation with a rapidly urbanising population, faces persistent challenges in its electricity sector, ranging from high system losses to revenue shortfalls and intermittent power supply often colloquially referred to as "dumsor" (Eshun & Amoako-Tuffour, 2016; Ahmed & Bruns, 2024). In Ghana, prepaid metering emerged as a prominent strategy to regulate the systemic inefficiencies in electricity distribution for enhanced revenue recovery. State-owned enterprises largely dominate the electricity sector. The Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG) holds the primary mandate for electricity distribution within the southern sector of the country. In a deliberate move to tackle ECG's operational and financial challenges, the company embarked on a nationwide rollout of prepaid metering systems, particularly targeting urban centres within its operational areas (PURC, 2019). Thus, since its widespread introduction by ECG, prepaid metering has gained traction in urban centres, particularly among residential users.

However, the implementation of the metering project has not been without significant social complexities. The new prepaid billing system greatly alters the relationship between the consumer and their energy supply by shifting the financial burden upfront. Hence, one critical concern with its adoption revolves around consumer vulnerability and the propensity for undesirable behaviours such as power theft. Despite its intended benefits, the deployment of prepaid meters has triggered growing concerns about its unintended economic and safety consequences arising from power theft, particularly for economically vulnerable consumers in urban areas, as opposed to urban sustainability (under Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 7 and 11) which emphasizes the importance of inclusive access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy, as well as the creation of resilient, equitable urban communities.

In Ghanaian urban settlements, socio-economic conditions vary widely, and a significant portion of the population faces fluctuating incomes and cost-of-living pressures, which makes the management of a prepaid electricity budget challenging (Bloomer & Boateng, 2024; Adusah-Poku & Takeuchi, 2019). The perceived high cost of electricity can inadvertently create incentives for illicit activities, including illegal connections or meter tampering (Effah & Owusu, 2014). Such actions may inflict substantial long-term damage on the utility's financial

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health and compromise communities' well-being. It equally undermines the sustainability of the national electricity grid, thereby curtailing energy access which impacts on urban human settlements (United Nations, 2025).

Furthermore, while prepaid systems offer transparent real-time consumption data, their deployment may generate issues regarding the quality-of-service (QOS) delivery. Some contentious issues include perceived rapid unit consumption, technical malfunctions of the meters, difficulties in accessing vending points, delays in fault resolution related to meter issues and a general lack of clarity on meter consumption. These issues, if pervasive, can erode consumer trust, thereby hindering the objective of developing sustainable and user-friendly urban infrastructure.

This study, therefore, investigates whether prepaid metering in selected marginalised urban cities in Ghana leads to consumer vulnerability behaviours and the policy implications of these behaviours on the utility sector and human settlements in the country. We emphasise the implications for consumer vulnerability and quality-of-service (QOS) complaints in Ghana.

The study focuses on six selected urban regions out of 8 under ECG's operations due to the unavailability of data for the remaining regions. Study regions include: Ashanti Regions (Cities: Manhyia and Ejisu), Western and Western North Regions (Cities: Takoradi and Sekondi), Eastern Region (Cities: Koforidua and New Tafo), Volta and Oti Regions (Cities: Ho and Hohoe). The cities for each region exhibit diverse socio-economic profiles, which creates an ideal context for comparative analysis.

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Figure 1 ECG's Operational Regions

Source: Ghana Audit Service (2023)

The specific objectives of the study are two-fold:

- i. Examine the relationship between prepaid meter deployment and consumer vulnerability behaviours (specifically, power theft).
- ii. Assess the impact of prepaid metering on the incidence of quality-of-service complaints by consumers.

2.0 Literature Review

ECG was founded in 1963 and sold its shares in 1967 to become a limited liability company. It continued to be the only organisation in charge of providing and distributing energy throughout southern Ghana since 1987 (Ghana Audit Service, 2023). From 2016 to 2020, electricity supply in Ghana added almost GHC9.4 billion to Ghana's GDP; yet, frequent power outages and technical and commercial power losses persisted. ECG oversaw the installation of pre-paid meters during this time to account for the losses, particularly those incurred by businesses. Despite the interventions, such as installing meters in 2020 to lower commercial losses from 13% to 10.5%, which is expected to save the corporation over \$42 million annually for the next eight years, ECG continues to experience large commercial losses. (Ghana Audit Service, 2023). The Millennium Development Authority (MIDA) provides ECG with a Meter Management System (MMS) as part of the Millennium Challenge Account (MCA), which intends to solve the problem of consumer power theft by collecting data in real time (Ghana Audit Service, 2023).

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To measure performance from the end-user's perspective, ECG started conducting customer satisfaction surveys in 2014 to determine the effects of its operations on consumers. The Company established the goal of satisfying 70% of its customers by the end of 2020. Although the customer satisfaction score steadily improved from 53.3% in 2014 to 63.7% in 2019, it fell short, reaching 63.80% in 2021 and 62.22% in 2024. Per the last survey conducted in 2024, non-payment of bills accounted for 26.83% of the reasons consumers were disconnected from the ECG grid (Electricity Company of Ghana, 2025).

According to the PURC 2016-2017 annual report, most customer complaints pertained to the subpar customer service provided by ECG employees. Consumers reported that the utilities took a long time to resolve many issues, including overbilling, bulk charging, and incorrect meter readings. The most common concern from customers, accounting for 59% of all complaints submitted to the Commission, was over-billing. In 2017, wrong bills issued to customers, untimely delivery of bills, and bulk billing of customers were among the most reported cases (PURC, 2017). Data from the PURC 2019 report indicates that the number of complaints filed against utilities, including ECG, decreased from 3,202 in 2016 to 2,713 in 2017. However, in 2018, the number rose to 5,226 (a 92.63% increase); in 2019, it rose to 9,550 (a 96.97% increase). In 2019, complaints about ECG's quality of service accounted for 30.24% of all complaints, making it the second most commonly reported issue. Within this group, most complainants expressed dissatisfaction with delays in new service connections and the stability of the power supplied by ECG. Metering issues accounted for 7.18% of all complaints against ECG, making it the third most common concern (PURC, 2020).

The most common complaint filed with the Commission as of 2021 was on Quality of Service, accounting for 75.80% of all complaints received. Metering complaints accounted for 4.74% of all complaints, with 2.42% attributed to payment problems and 1.48% to unlawful disconnection, which is defined as disconnection without notice (PURC, 2021).

2.1 Conceptual Framework

This study's conceptual framework is built on the interaction between prepaid meter deployment and two key outcome variables: consumer vulnerability behaviour (power theft) and quality of service experience (frequency of complaints). The framework posits that while prepaid metering is intended to improve efficiency in revenue assurance, it may also trigger unintended outcomes, particularly in urban-poor communities. The framework is also anchored within the contexts of SDGs 7 and 11. It therefore provides a lens through which the regulatory impact of prepaid metering can be evaluated on sustainable urban living.

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Figure 2 Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors' Construct, 2025

2.2 Theoretical Underpinnings

The study is already anchored in the SDGs, specifically SDG 7 (affordable, reliable energy) and SDG 11 (sustainable cities). The SDGs serve as the overarching policy and social development framework to evaluate the societal impacts of prepaid metering. Concerning SDG 7, the study assesses whether prepaid meters, while ensuring revenue for the utility, are truly making energy more affordable and reliable for all consumers, especially the most vulnerable. It can measure affordability in terms of price per unit and the financial strain on customers, which may push them to steal electricity. It also measures the impact on reliability through the quality-of-service complaints recorded over the study period. For SDG 11, the framework allows for evaluating how prepaid metering affects urban life. By linking the meters to behaviours like power theft and quality of service complaints, the study can assess if the system contributes to or detracts from the goal of making cities resilient and sustainable.

2.3 Empirical Review

Wagner and Wiegand (2018) conducted Germany's first scientific survey on prepayment meters (PPMs), which was prompted by rising energy poverty and increasing power disconnections. The study concentrated on poor households and welfare recipients, exploring the prevalence and consequences of "self-disconnection" when households cannot afford to top up their meters. The research cautions that while prepaid meters can appear to address energy poverty by enabling debt control, they risk masking the deeper structural problem of unaffordable energy. Although Germany's strong social safety nets moderate the severity of impacts compared to developing contexts, their findings' behavioural and equity perspectives offer insights to the Ghanaian context.

O'Sullivan, Viggers, and Howden-Chapman (2014) examined similar themes in New Zealand, using qualitative interviews with 30 prepaid-using households. Like Wagner and Wiegand (2018), O'Sullivan, *et al* (2014) found self-disconnection a common and harmful consequence, particularly for families with young children. However, their emphasis on the "lumpy" nature

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of electricity usage and payment system added a behavioural dimension that was absent from the German study. Both studies converge in warning that PPMs can exacerbate energy vulnerability, but diverge in that O’Sullivan et al. foreground health and well-being impacts, while Wagner and Wiegand frame the issue through structural affordability.

Mathenge (2015) studied Thika Sub-County in Kenya and identified a more optimistic consumer reception. The study discovered that prepaid metering improved expenditure control and budgeting and reduced billing disputes. Yet, similar to the prior studies, low-income households faced disconnection risks. A distinct finding absent in the German and New Zealand cases was an environmental trade-off by customers who were recorded to shift from electricity to biomass cooking; they accounted for 21% of households. In Alao, Jimoh, and Obadiora (2022), it was found predominantly that positive perceptions of prepaid meters existed in Nigeria’s Ile-Ife Metropolis, with 76.4% reporting satisfaction. Still, poor households experienced electricity only when they could afford credit, mirroring the same vulnerability patterns observed in Germany and New Zealand.

Ghanaian studies by Tuffour et al. (2018) and Oforiwaa (2017) revealed mixed perceptions. While the former emphasised efficiency gains and consumer “freedom,” the latter reported adoption barriers from inadequate consumer education. Both, however, agree that information gaps undermine optimal usage of prepaid meters. This theme was less pronounced in high-income country studies but critical within the African contexts.

Collectively, these studies show that prepaid meters consistently improve billing transparency and expenditure control, but across contexts, they can also concentrate disconnection risks among the poor. Divergences emerge in the secondary effects: environmental shifts in Kenya, health impacts in New Zealand and informational deficits in Ghana. This cross-contextual evidence proves that regulatory frameworks must account for affordability, education, and unintended socio-economic consequences of prepaid meter adoption for sustainable urban living.

3.0 Methodology

This section details the data, variables, and techniques used to achieve the study's objectives.

3.1 Data and Methodology

The study adheres to a positivist research philosophy and a quantitative research technique. It operates from an objectivist epistemology, assuming that a meaningful reality exists and can be empirically investigated. We used yearly panel data from 2017 to 2021, sourced from several key institutions: the Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana Audit Service, the Public Utilities Regulatory Commission (PURC), and the Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG). The analysis is focused on four ECG operational regions where essential data on prepaid meter deployment were available. Due to a reclassification of administrative regions in Ghana in 2019, some of the original 10 regions were split. Divided regions were subsequently merged for this study to maintain consistency for the panel data analysis. The four regions under examination are:

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- i. Ashanti Region
- ii. Western Region (combining Western and Western North for data beyond 2019)
- iii. Eastern Region
- iv. Volta Region (combining Volta and Oti for data beyond 2019)

Table 1. Variables, Data Sources and Expected Signs.

Variable	Description	Source	Expected sign	Units of Measure
PT	Power theft by customers	Ghana Audit Service Report		Ghana Cedi (GHC)
MD	Meter Deployment to customers	Ghana Audit Service Report	Positive	Number of meters
NE	Net enrollment at the Senior High School (SHS) Level	Ghana Statistical Service	Negative	Rate of persons enrolled in SHS
QOSC	Quality of Service Complaints from Customers	PURC Annual Report	Positive	Number of complaints
DC	Unlawful Disconnection of customers	PURC Annual Report	Positive	Number of Complaints
MC	Meter faults Complaints	PURC Annual Report	Positive	Number of Complaints
BC	Billing Inconsistency Complaints	PURC Annual Report	Positive	Number of Complaints

Source: Authors' Compilation, 2025

The expected signs are based on the hypothesis that increased Meter Deployment (MD) may lead to a rise in Power Theft (PT) and Quality of Service Complaints (QOSC). Conversely, a higher net enrollment (NE) rate is expected to have a mitigating effect on power theft, as education is a proxy for economic stability and a better understanding of the formal energy system. Similarly, increases in specific complaint types (DC, MC, BC) are anticipated to positively correlate with overall complaints.

3.2 Estimation techniques

To analyse the panel data and account for unobserved heterogeneity, this study employs two static panel-estimation methodologies: Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE) models, consistent with established econometric practices (Lončar et al., 2021; Sebki, 2021; Perles et al., 2022). The FE model addresses endogeneity by controlling for time-invariant unobserved characteristics specific to each region, thereby reducing bias. While assuming that the unobserved effects are uncorrelated with the explanatory variables, the RE model offers greater efficiency under this assumption. The Hausman test will determine the more appropriate model for the data. The data were analysed using Stata 17 software.

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The empirical model follows the works of Gershon et al (2024) and Anser et al (2020). Below are the empirical models for the study objectives:

Impact of Meter Deployment on Power Theft

$$(1) \text{Meter Theft}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MD_{i,t} + \beta_2 NE_{i,t} + \beta_3 DC_{i,t} + \beta_4 QOSC_{i,t} + \beta_5 MC_{i,t} + \beta_6 BC_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Impact of Meter Deployment on Quality-of-Service Complaints

$$(2) \text{Quality of Service}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MD_{i,t} + \beta_2 NE_{i,t} + \beta_3 PT_{i,t} + \beta_4 BC_{i,t} + \beta_5 BC_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Region and time are denoted by subscripts t and i, respectively.

4.0 Results and Analysis

Figure 3 below reveals a consistent trend of decreasing average household size across all regions from 2010 to 2021, with a stark regional disparity in household size. The urbanised southern regions, including the Volta, decreased from 4.0 to 3.3. In contrast, the Oti region started with a larger average of 5.0. It decreased to 4.2. Eastern (4.2 to 3.2), Western dropping from 4.2 to 3.3, Western North from 4.6 to 3.6, and Ashanti (4.2 to 3.4) show smaller average household sizes. According to the figure, smaller household sizes can proxy for lower overall energy demand and potentially reduced financial strain on the household head. As power theft is often a behaviour of last resort triggered by an inability to manage prepaid meter budgets, it could be hypothesised that these smaller households may have a lower propensity for power theft.

Figure 3: Average Regional Household Size

Data Source: Ghana Statistical Services (2022)

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Figure 4 shows a common trend for the four regions: Eastern, Ashanti, Volta and Western. The data reveal a consistent "U-shaped" unemployment curve across all four regions, with the highest rates occurring in the youth age bracket (15-24) and again for older citizens. This high youth unemployment, particularly peaking in the 20-24 age group, is a decisive indicator of economic vulnerability within these urban areas. High unemployment directly translates to fluctuating or non-existent incomes, which makes it challenging for households to manage the upfront financial burden of prepaid metering. Accordingly, this demographic factor is likely a significant driver of consumer vulnerability behaviours such as power theft and could lead to a higher frequency of complaints related to affordability and perceived rapid unit consumption. Regional variations exist, with the Volta and Western regions showing slightly higher unemployment than Eastern and Ashanti.

Figure 4 Unemployment Rate in 2021, by Region and Age

Data Source: Ghana Statistical Service (2024)

Figure 5 below clearly indicates an overwhelming reliance on electricity for light in all four regions, with Ashanti having the highest number of households using this source (over 1,200,000). The other regions also show a widespread adoption of electricity compared to other light sources. This high reliance on electricity confirms that many consumers in these urban areas are directly subject to the prepaid metering system. However, the chart also reveals a small but significant number of households across all regions that still rely on non-electric sources for light, such as Flashlight/Torchlight, Solar lamps, Candles, and Kerosene lamps. This small segment of the population may be more susceptible to consumer vulnerability, potentially due to economic hardship. It means that access to affordable and modern energy (SDG 7) remains a challenge, which could lead to consumer vulnerability behaviours. On a regional basis, Ashanti and Eastern have fewer households using lighting alternatives, but Volta and Western regions show a higher number of households using sources like flashlights and candles; hence, households in Volta and Western might be more susceptible to the financial pressures of prepaid metering.

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Figure 5 Household Source of Lighting by Regions (2021)

Data Source 1 Ghana Statistical Service (2024)

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 below presents the descriptive statistics for this study's variables. Power theft cases recorded an average of approximately Ghana Cedi (Ghc) 2.7 million, with substantial variability of about 3.96 million, ranging from zero to a peak of 14.3 million. Meter deployment averaged 27,715 units, with values ranging from 5,412 to 86,480 units, reflecting significant differences in rollout intensity across regions and years. The net enrolment rate averaged 28.51%, with a minimum of 3.8% and a maximum of 51.8%, indicating notable disparities in educational access within the study regions. Regarding service-related grievances, quality of service complaints averaged 471 cases annually, with a wide spread between 24 and 1,499 cases. Disconnection complaints were relatively lower, averaging 23 cases but reaching as high as 71 in some years. Metering complaints averaged 61 annually, with a minimum of 9 and a maximum of 159, while billing complaints were the most prevalent among complaint categories, averaging 318 cases and peaking at 915. The statistics provide an overview of the magnitude and variability of factors influencing prepaid metering and its regulatory implications for sustainable urban living.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Power Theft	2699423	3955067	0	14300000
Meter Deployment	27715	19103.07	5412	86480

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Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Net Enrolment Rate	28.505	14.95007	3.8	51.8
Quality Of Service Complaints	471.3125	437.047	24	1499
Disconnection Complaints	23.375	16.53229	3	71
Metering Complaints	61.25	45.96593	9	159
Billing Complaints	318	245.9969	38	915

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix provides information about the likelihood of multicollinearity among the variables. The results indicate that the independent variables are not highly correlated, with the highest correlation among the primary explanatory variables being between Net Enrolment and Billing Complaints (0.429), a value well below the threshold for multicollinearity concerns.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Power Theft	1						
Meter Deployment	0.1783	1					
Net Enrolment	-0.255	-0.063	1				
Quality Of Service Complaints	-0.0297	-0.1223	-0.0062	1			
Disconnection Complaints	-0.0218	0.0306	-0.2456	-0.3549	1		
Metering Complaints	-0.1189	0.1002	-0.2053	-0.084	0.5676	1	
Billing Complaints	-0.2698	0.1223	0.429	-0.0902	0.3005	0.4586	1

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

4.3 Empirical estimation and discussion of the results

The findings of the static panel estimate are provided and analyzed in this section within the context of the literature. Table 4 below presents the estimated results from both the fixed effects and random effects models assessing the relationship between prepaid meter deployment and reported cases of power theft. The Hausman specification test indicates that the fixed effects model is more appropriate for consistent estimation, given the rejection of the null hypothesis that random effects would yield consistent results.

Table 4. Impact of Prepaid Meter Deployment on Power Theft

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Variables	Fixed Effect	Random Effect
Meter Deployment (l)	2.469**	2.712***
Net Enrolment (%)	0.055**	0.053***
Quality Of Service Complaints	-0.00022	-0.0013***
Disconnection Complaints	-0.0017	0.0086
Metering Complaints	0.0096	-.00078
Billing Complaints	-0.0013	-.0028***
Constant	-10.22*	-12.30***
Wald chi2(7)		106.72
Prob > chi2		0.000
Prob>F	0.0743*	
Sigma u	.90017082	0
Sigma e	.32228666	.32228666
Rho	.88638001	0
Hausman Specification chi2(6)	23.48	
Prob > chi2	0.0007	

Source: Authors' computation, 2025 [*Statistical significance, t statistics in parentheses*
* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$]

4.4 Regression Findings (1)

The coefficients for meter deployment are both positive and statistically significant in the Fixed Effects (2.469, $p < 0.05$) and Random Effects (2.712, $p < 0.01$) models. Contrary to the common policy narrative that prepaid meters reduce theft and losses, this positive association suggests that higher levels of meter deployment correspond with higher reported cases of power theft within the study context. It may indicate that prepaid meters, when deployed without adequate enforcement and anti-tampering measures, are vulnerable to bypassing or manipulation, particularly in socio-economically challenged urban communities.

Net enrolment in Senior High School (SHS) also shows a positive and highly significant relationship with power theft in fixed effects. This finding is counterintuitive to the expectation that higher education reduces engagement in illicit practices. It may reflect that better technical literacy inadvertently facilitates tampering with meters in urban and peri-urban communities with higher SHS enrolment.

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The results for Quality of Service (QOS) complaints show a negligible and statistically insignificant coefficient under Fixed Effects (-0.00022) but a small, negative, and statistically significant association in the Random Effects model (-0.0013, $p < 0.01$). For disconnection complaints, the results are mixed; negative and insignificant under Fixed Effects (-0.0017) but positive and insignificant under Random Effects (0.0086). Metering complaints have mixed signs and are statistically insignificant across both models, indicating they do not systematically explain theft incidence in the sample. Similarly, billing complaints display negative coefficients, with the random effects estimate being significant. It proposes that fewer billing-related grievances correspond with lower theft rates in the pooled setting. The model diagnostics show high within-unit variance explained in the fixed effects model ($\rho = 0.886$), signifying substantial variation in theft across regions over time. The Wald chi-square statistic of 106.72 confirms overall model significance.

The findings reveal a paradox: prepaid meter deployment, intended as an anti-theft measure, appears to correlate with higher theft incidence, with education levels (SHS enrolment) amplifying this effect.

Table 5. Impact of Prepaid Meter Deployment on Quality-of-Service Complaints

Variables	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
Meter Deployment (l)	3.835*	4.131***
Net Enrolment (1)	1.201	1.328***
Power Theft	-1.923*	-1.1467***
Billing Complaints	-1.163	-0.855***
Constant	-1.634	-13.193***
Wald chi2(7)		28.89
Prob > chi2		0.000
Prob>F	0.1540	
Sigma u	.97347072	0
Sigma e	.67514531	.67514531
Rho	.67521761	
Hausman Specification chi2(4)	2.08	
Prob > chi2	0.7211	

Source: Authors' computation, 2025 [*Statistical significance, t statistics in parentheses*
* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$]

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4.5 Regression Findings (2)

The regression results in Table 5 depict a Hausman specification test result ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.7211$), revealing that the Random Effects model is the more appropriate estimator for this analysis. The analysis shows that prepaid meter deployment has a statistically significant and positive effect on the number of quality-of-service complaints, with a coefficient of 4.131 under the random effects model. This indicates that as prepaid meters are deployed, there is a tendency for complaints relating to service quality to increase, which could be explained by the initial operational challenges and consumer adaptation issues that often accompany prepaid meter rollouts, such as meter malfunction, communication failures between meters and utility systems or perceived service interruptions tied to credit depletion. While prepaid metering is intended to improve operational efficiency and consumer transparency, these results suggest that deployment could inadvertently lead to an unfriendly user experience without robust technical support and consumer sensitization.

The findings also show that net enrolment rates in senior high schools are statistically significant under the random effects model, with a coefficient of 1.328. This could reflect the role of higher educational enrolment in the expectations for consistent service, potentially increasing the propensity to lodge complaints when services fall short. Furthermore, the coefficient for Power Theft, which is -0.1467, is negative and highly significant. This proposes that as power theft increases, the number of Quality-of-Service complaints tends to decrease. It strongly implies that consumers engaging in illicit activities are less likely to formally complain to the utility company or regulator about service issues. Billing Complaints show a negative and significant coefficient of -0.855, which might seem contradictory. However, this is likely because Billing Complaints are already a sub-component of the total Quality-of-Service Complaints, so a high number of one specific type of complaint might not necessarily lead to a corresponding increase in the aggregated total.

4.6 Discussion and Policy Implications

For the first objective of this study, which sought to assess the impact of prepaid meter deployment on power theft in urban Ghana, the positive and statistically significant coefficient for meter deployment indicates, contrary to the common policy expectation, that increased meter deployment is associated with higher reported cases of power theft. High numbers of unemployed individuals in Ashanti (275,942), Western (163,858), Eastern (135,352) and Volta (101,536) reveal widespread economic vulnerability across the study regions. Managing a prepaid electricity budget is challenging for these populations, especially with fluctuating or non-existent incomes. The prepaid system's demand for upfront payment creates financial pressure, which, for a vulnerable consumer, can lead to engaging in power theft as a coping mechanism.

From an energy policy perspective, this relationship implies that current metering strategies may be unintentionally fuelling a cycle of losses in the electricity sector. Power theft directly contributes to revenue shortfalls for utilities, increasing the accumulation of sector debt. Such financial deficits eventually place upward pressure on electricity tariffs as utilities and regulators seek to recover costs, creating a regressive impact on low-income households, especially in the densely populated and economically vulnerable urban areas, as indicated in

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the study, such as Manhyia and Ejisu in the Ashanti Region, Takoradi and Sekondi in the Western Region, Koforidua and New Tafo in the Eastern Region, Ho and Hohoe in the Volta Region. Such an outcome could undermine the operational efficiency of the Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG) and stall progress toward achieving reliable, sustainable energy access as envisioned under SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy).

Moreover, higher tariffs driven by commercial power losses can push households, especially in low-income segments of urban cities, to seek alternative energy sources, many of which are unclean, such as charcoal or firewood. This exacerbates environmental degradation and carbon emissions. This erodes the health and safety benefits of modern energy access in urban settlements with persistent emissions (Gershon, Asafo, Sowah & Tanko, 2025). The study by Mathenge (2015) in Kenya provides a relevant parallel, where a significant percentage of households switched from electricity to charcoal for cooking. This behaviour, likely to be mirrored in Ghana's urban-poor communities, will undermine the sustainability objectives of SDG 7 and SDG 11. Likewise, in congested urban neighbourhoods that perpetrate illegal connections, the poorly executed wiring may lead to fires, electrocutions and other hazards that threaten lives and property, further straining health services in these already overburdened areas. These dynamic challenges Ghana's commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Regarding SDG 7 (affordable, reliable, and modern energy). The current prepaid metering policy, rather than ensuring access, appears to make electricity unaffordable for a segment of the population, forcing them into illicit activities to maintain their energy supply. Furthermore, for SDG 11 (inclusive, safe, and sustainable cities), the policy's unintended consequence of increasing power theft compromises the urban communities' safety and energy infrastructure.

For the second objective, which investigates the influence of meter deployment on quality-of-service complaints, the results reveal strong policy implications for improving power reliability within Southern Ghana's urban cities. The findings suggest that while prepaid systems can enhance revenue assurance, inadequate preparation in their implementation can be a direct measure of perceived unreliability from the consumer's perspective. In congested metropolitan areas such as Ashanti and parts of the Western and Eastern Regions, reliability issues linked to meter malfunctions, signal failures or unexpected credit depletion may trigger frequent disruptions for vulnerable households. Sometimes, the abrupt disconnection of power due to the inability of customers to top up a prepaid meter constitutes a major service interruption and a failure of reliability to them, leading to a rise in consumer grievances that undermine the goal of ensuring access to reliable energy, potentially leading to illicit activities like power theft that further compromise the safety and resilience of congested urban communities.

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the regulatory impact of prepaid metering on sustainable urban living in selected regions of Ghana, focusing on its relationship with consumer vulnerability behaviours, specifically power theft, and quality-of-service complaints. Using panel data from 2017 to 2021

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across four ECG operational regions, the study applied Fixed Effects and Random Effects econometric models for regression analysis. The study provides evidence that prepaid meter deployment was positively and significantly associated with increased cases of power theft. Second, prepaid meter deployment was also positively and significantly linked to higher quality-of-service complaints. These findings challenge the assumption that prepaid meters improve efficiency and service satisfaction. We therefore highlight the need for policy reforms that integrate stronger consumer education, targeted support for vulnerable households and improved technical maintenance systems for prepaid meters.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

The Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG) should prioritise deploying advanced prepaid metering technology with remote anti-tampering capabilities. This will help in curbing electricity theft stemming from unauthorised reconnections. In parallel, the company should strengthen its fault response systems, ensuring that faults and disconnection errors are resolved promptly to maintain consumer trust in the system. ECG should also maintain its targeted interventions for low-income households (the lifeline tariff structures) and consider bringing emergency credit options on board to prevent disconnections that could push consumers towards illegal connections. Furthermore, the company improve the transparency in its billing structure and promote responsible energy use through communal campaigns. Lastly, the company can consider working with its regulators, the PURC and Energy Commission (EC), to develop a legal framework for guiding meter deployment in Ghana, whilst formulating benchmarks for performance monitoring of the prepaid meters, as Ghana currently does not possess one. These benchmarks can be integrated into a computerised system to monitor real-time data on theft, losses, and customer satisfaction and guide future operational adjustments.

The Public Utilities Regulatory Commission (PURC) should work with ECG and EC to develop meter deployment and usage benchmarks and regulations. In addition, PURC could enhance transparency and accountability by requiring ECG to publish yearly performance reports on prepaid metering, including data on units deployed, revenue recovered, loss reduction units and customer service metrics. Finally, the Commission should continue facilitating multi-stakeholder dialogue by bringing together utilities, consumer groups, technology providers and policymakers to ensure prepaid metering remains responsive to consumer needs and contributes meaningfully to Ghana's sustainable urban development.

The ECG and the Public Utilities Regulatory Commission should therefore consider future policy which moves beyond simply deploying meters for revenue recovery and adopts a more holistic, socio-economically sensitive strategy. The above recommendations emphasise the need for urban utility reforms integrated with urban planning to support socially inclusive, resilient and sustainable living. Furthermore, the recommendations will enhance electricity access and the long-term sustainability of life in urban human settlements

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